

THE ROLE OF IOT (INTERNET OF THINGS) IN MODERNIZING TECHNIQUES: BUILDING SMART HOUSES AND CITIES

Abdimuratova Nargiza

*Affiliation: Ajou University in Tashkent, department of
Electrical and Computer Engineering*

Email: ajouplatform@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17066782>

Abstract. *The Internet of Things (IoT) is a transformative technology that defines interaction of environment to technology enabling devices and systems to connect, exchange information and operate. With its most impactful applications it has already become inseparable step of reshaping the way people live. This article reviews recently made changes and examples to define the role of IoT technologies in real life utilizes and process of roadmap of future Smart City. It also examines Uzbekistan's current initiatives in smart metering and digital transformation. Findings highlight that IoT in smart houses improves energy management, security, health monitoring, and overall convenience, while IoT in smart cities enhances traffic control, waste management, public safety, and environmental controlling. Despite these advantages, challenges such as cybersecurity risks, high infrastructure costs, and device interoperability remain critical concerns.*

Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) extends the power of the internet beyond computers and smartphones to everyday objects such as household appliances, cars, medical devices, and even entire city infrastructures. By enables sensors, processors, and communication technologies to connect physical items and operate upon data with minimal human interaction. It is not only diminishing human input in technology, but a fundamental transformation towards smarter and data-driven lifestyle. Industry analysts shows that by 2030, the number of connected IoT devices could grow to 40 billion, generating unprecedented amounts of data and unlocking new opportunities for innovation across sectors. For example, improving healthcare through remote patient monitoring and creating healthy life for patients, creating more connected appliances to provide comfort, security and efficiency. On a larger scale, smart cities implement IoT systems across transportation, energy, public services to improve quality of urban life.

On its base, it works depending on the main four elements: sensors and devices, data processing, connectivity and user interfaces. Sensors gather information from surrounding such as temperature, motion, or heart rate and transmit this information via wireless technologies like Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, or cellular networks. The data is proceeded locally, if more complex tasks

should be operated, it is be transmitted to cloud servers. After all analysis are finished, the information is represented to users through smartphone or automated system applications. A simple example of this process is a smart thermostat. The device senses room temperature, transmits the data to a central system, and then adjusts the heating or cooling automatically based on user preferences.

Methods.

This article is based on review approach, drawing information from variety of credible sources including academic journals, authentic websites, and real time usages of smart appliances. Case studies of recent year technologies used both in houses and public. Data were obtained from different websites including *Digital Uzbekistan 2030*, statistical analysis and market trends. By combining all gathered information with real-time examples, this method offers a comprehensive understanding of IoT’s role in modernizing smart houses and smart cities.

Results.

IoT in Smart Houses

IoT has revolutionized the concept of housing by transforming traditional residences into intelligent, adaptive living spaces. The most significant applications include: energy management, security, comfort and health improving.

With the help of intelligent appliances, daily intake of user is learned is adjusted to consumption automatically. So that, energy and extra product will be saved. About security, IoT can be surely believed with cameras, smart locks, and motion sensors that provide real-time monitoring and remote access to home security systems. Besides, devices such as Amazon Alexa and Google Nest integrate appliances, lighting, and entertainment systems into voice-controlled hubs that avoid extra act and discomfort. And earlier mentioned and most important task is health monitoring. Wireless devices and IoT-enabled systems connect health data directly to home networks, offering real-time monitoring for chronic patients to keep fit and healthy. These all leads to incredible expenditure of smart technologies in households and making life easier and convenient.

IoT in Smart Cities

Smart technologies cover all areas in developed cities, including traffic and transportation, energy management, safety and monitoring. Since IoT is integrated with artificial intelligence, it can make decisions in real fast pace. In result, IoT enabled traffic lights, connected vehicles and GPS-based transport systems reduce congestion and act safely. Similarly, streetlights with IoT sensors get information of brightness and adjust lights based on movement or natural light, reducing energy consumption. Cameras on the streets records all the happenings and at some points could prevent upcoming accidents. Cities use IoT-based sensors to track air pollution, noise, and water quality in real time. Accordingly, based on the results they receive, citizens can use other appliances to protect their health in advance.

Discussion.

The results demonstrate that IoT is a central point for the development of both smart houses and smart cities. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also currently implementing new strategies to develop digital economy, as well as widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies covering all sectors and areas, especially public services, education, healthcare and agriculture. Due to a vast opportunities created, 10 million citizens

used digital services in 2024, and, currently, 760 types of government services have been digitalized.

Advantages

IoT brings opportunities to create comfortable, safe life and greater management over energy, quantity. People benefit from access to home appliances from a distance and making life easier with automation. In smart cities, IoT contributes to sustainability, improved mobility, and better public services, addressing key challenges of urbanization.

Challenges

Despite the benefits, IoT also presents critical concerns. Cybersecurity and privacy risks are major issues, as billions of connected devices are vulnerable to hacking. Interoperability between devices from different manufacturers is often limited, slowing large-scale integration. Additionally, infrastructure costs for smart cities remain high, requiring significant investment from governments and private sectors.

Future Outlook

The collaboration of artificial intelligence, blockchain and 5G internet speed will further strengthen IoT systems, contributing to its faster, safer, and more intelligent working level. This combination would protect both nature, by reducing energy waste, and human data and health. Smart cities of the future are expected to integrate autonomous transportation, fully digital governance, and AI-based public services. As a result, public vehicles will be safe, services can be accomplished quickly, and the nature will be saved.

Conclusion.

IoT has become cornerstone in urbanization and modernization. By enabling communication between devices and systems, it improves efficiency, enhances safety, and helps sustainable living. Even though difficulties in cybersecurity, cost and other details occur, technological advancements rapidly address these limitations. The future of IoT lies in improving safety, comfortability, and creating fast and convenient services to public. Ultimately, IoT is not only technology, but innovation of smart cities of tomorrow.

REFERENCES

1. Sharon Shea, • July 16, 2020 Smart cities
<https://www.techtargget.com/iotagenda/definition/smart-city>
2. Kinza Yasar, Technical Writer, Sharon Shea, Jul 31, 2025
<https://www.techtargget.com/iotagenda/definition/smart-home-or-building>
3. Satyajit Sinha September 3, 2024 State of IoT 2024: Number of connected IoT devices growing 13% to 18.8 billion globally <https://iot-analytics.com/number-connected-iot-devices/>
4. *Digital Uzbekistan 2030* <https://lex.uz/docs/5031048>